

CodeReef and MLPerf demo: keeping up with AI, ML and systems innovation with portable workflows and collaborative benchmarking

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A live interactive demo: [CodeReef.ai/demo](https://codereef.ai/demo)

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Abstract

We will demonstrate how to use our open CodeReef platform ([CodeReef.ai/portal](https://codereef.ai/portal)) with open-source CodeReef solutions - a new way to share ML models as non-virtualized, portable, customizable and reusable packages. Such packages contain portable workflows with JSON input/output, CLI and Python API, software detection plugins, meta packages and pre-/post-processing scripts to automatically build, benchmark, test and customize ML-based applications across diverse platforms, environments, AI/ML frameworks, libraries, compilers and data sets. We will help participants to test several real-world CodeReef solutions to automatically build, reproduce, collaboratively benchmark and compare several recent MLPerf inference submissions (mlperf.org/inference-results) across a wide range of platforms from Raspberry Pi and Android phones to HPC servers with powerful GPUs. Our long-term goal is to help the community keep track of ML and systems innovation and facilitate research by sharing ML models and all related research artifacts along with research papers as production-ready CodeReef solutions which can be immediately used for collaborative benchmarking and reproducible comparison of ML, software and hardware stacks.

Keywords: *portable workflows, non-virtualized components, automation, reproducibility, reusability, research automation, collaborative benchmarking, cross-platform MLOps, MLSysOps, AIOps, collective knowledge*

1 Introduction

While helping companies to move the state-of-the-art ML models found at ArXiv, PapersWithCode and MLPerf to production we have noticed that finding the related code is only a tip of the iceberg. The major challenge afterwards is to figure out how to install ML models, integrate them with complex (legacy) applications, customize them and run them in the most efficient way across numerous and rapidly evolving heterogeneous systems with continuously changing interfaces and data formats while balancing multiple characteristics including speed, latency, accuracy, memory size, power consumption, reliability and various costs.

Existing tools such as MLFlow, Kedro and Amazon SageMaker focus mainly on the automation of training and other high-level ML operations while Docker, Kubernetes and other container based tools are useful to hide software chaos rather than solving it, rarely target embedded devices and do not help to integrate models with native environments and user data.

All these problems motivated us to develop [CodeReef.ai/portal](https://codereef.ai/portal) - a collaborative platform

inspired by GitHub and PyPI to share portable ML components and workflows along with reproduced ML results. It is based on the open-source Collective Knowledge technology (CK, github.com/ctuning/ck) with open standards to let users exchange all the basic blocks (components) needed to assemble portable ML workflows and collaboratively benchmark and compare their performance using customizable dashboards. We decided to use the open and non-virtualized CK format because it is a proven open-source technology used in many academic and industrial projects during the past 4 years: cKnowledge.org/partners. For example, the authors of 18 research papers from different systems and ML conferences used CK to share their research artifacts with automated workflows: [CodeReef.ai/portal/search/?q="portable-workflow-ck"](https://codereef.ai/portal/search/?q=)

CK helps to convert ad-hoc research projects into a file-based database of reusable components ([CodeReef.ai/portal/c/module](https://codereef.ai/portal/c/module)) including code, data, models, pre-/post-processing scripts, experimental results, best research practices to reproduce results, and auto-generated papers with unified Python APIs,

CLI-based automation actions (CodeReef.ai/portal/c/cr-action) and JSON meta information. CK also features plugins to automatically detect different software, models and data sets on a user machine or install the missing ones while supporting different operating systems (Linux, Windows, MacOS, Android) and hardware (Nvidia, Arm, Intel, AMD ...). Such approach allows researchers to create and share flexible APIs with JSON input/output for different AI/ML frameworks, libraries, compilers, models and data sets, connect them together into unified workflows instead of hardwired scripts, make them portable (CodeReef.ai/portal/c/program) using the automatic software detection plugins (CodeReef.ai/portal/c/soft) and meta-packages (CodeReef.ai/portal/c/package).

We developed CodeReef platform to provide a centralized place to aggregate, version, test and create all components and workflows necessary to enable reproducible ML benchmarking and portable MLOps (MLSysOps). Furthermore, the CodeReef technology is non-intrusive - it complements, abstracts and interconnects all existing tools including MLFlow, MLPerf, Docker and Kubernetes and make them more system aware rather than replacing or rewriting them.

2 Interactive demo: automating, sharing and reproducing MLPerf inference benchmarks

A prototype of our platform is now available at CodeReef.ai/portal. We started working with the community to share the state-of-the-art ML models as portable CodeReef solutions: CodeReef.ai/portal/c/cr-solution. We also collaborate with the MLPerf benchmarking consortium (MLPerf.org) to automate the manual and tedious process of creating MLPerf inference benchmarks and submitting results.

In this demo we will demonstrate the open-source CodeReef solution for the object detection application from the MLPerf inference benchmark based on SSD-Mobilenets, TensorFlow and COCO data-set. We will show how to use the open-source CodeReef Client (github.com/codereef-ai/client) with the unified CodeReef API to automatically build, run and validate this benchmark on a user machine.

We will also explain how to prepare and customize such solutions with a simple JSON manifest file (we plan to provide a GUI to simplify this process in the future) describing all the dependencies on CK components and APIs to automate the following tasks:

- download and install the Coco dataset (50 or 5000 images),
- install/cross-compile Tensorflow with a specified version for a given target machine,
- download and install the SSD-MobilNet model compatible with selected Tensorflow,

- compile object detection for a given machine and prepare pre/post-processing scripts.

After such solution is published at the CodeReef platform, anyone can download, initialize, run it and participate in crowd-benchmarking using their machine as follows:

1. install the open-source CodeReef client from PyPI using:

```
pip install codereef
```

2. download and install the solution on your machine (example for Linux):

```
cr init demo-obj-detection-coco-tf-cpu-benchmark-linux-portable-workflows
```

3. run the solution on your machine:

```
cr benchmark demo-obj-detection-coco-tf-cpu-benchmark-linux-portable-workflows
```

All participants will be able to see their measurements (speed, latency, accuracy) on the customizable CodeReef dashboard and compare them against the official MLPerf inference results at codereef.ai/portal/c/cr-result/sotamlperf-object-detection-v0.5-crowd-benchmarking.

After validating this solution on a given platform, users can check and collaboratively improve the portability of the solution using other devices and operating systems such as MacOS, Windows with Docker, Android phones, servers with CUDA-enabled GPUs and so on.

We will also demonstrate how to integrate CodeReef ML models with legacy systems and applications by integrating the above workflow with the live object detection from the web cam available at CodeReef.ai/portal/c/cr-solution/demo-obj-detection-coco-tf-cpu-webcam-linux-azure.

We are only at the beginning of this long-term community project and we hope that our demo will motivate researchers to share their ML models and research artifacts as portable, customizable, reproducible and reusable packages.